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“THE INVISIBLE SUNSET”

In the afternoon, I went to our dock and watched the sky melting into a sea of gold and crimson. This always help my soul to lighten my mood and get some fresh air. In my rumination, I looked behind me and I saw a man. He's older than me, I guess. His hair was well done, tall, and very handsome, but he looked grumpy. His wrinkled face told a tale of experience. His bland face seemed kind. I smiled at him, but his expression was still blank. He was carrying a walking stick, and when his brown eyes met mine, there's a weird feeling inside my stomach. Maybe it was the admiration of his demeanor. I looked back at the beautiful view and acted as if he wasn't behind me. I looked back at him and saw that he was gazing at the sunset. I noticed that other people were gawking at him. Not knowing why, I observed everyone. I was curious, but suddenly someone yelled, "Your blind, you can't see how beautiful the sunset is." I was surprised, and I just realized that's why he didn't smile back at me because he couldn't really see me. How can a blind person see the sunset?

He smirked then answered, "Maybe I can't see it but I can feel it. I can feel the air as it melodically brushes against my skin. I can sense the change of temperature as it fluctuates from warm to cool. These things tell me that the day itself is slipping away. It sends a quiet signal that the sun has dipped below the horizon and I can hope for a better tomorrow.

After that, he left dragging his fragile body. The tapping of the stick was the only sound I heard. As I stood there, I have never appreciated sunsets more than today.